

IMPACT RESISTANCE AND RESIDUAL COMPRESSION STRENGTH
OF COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

The effect of low energy impact damage on the edgewise compression strength of Graphite/Epoxy sandwich panels was determined experimentally. Several panels with $[\pm 45/0_2]_S$ Hercules IM8/8551-7A toughened epoxy facesheets were fabricated with various honeycomb core types including : Aluminum, Nomex, HRP Glass, NP Glass, and TPC (thermoplastic) Glass reinforced versions. Compression specimens of each panel type were impacted at levels of 2.7, 5.4, and 8.1 Joules (2,4, and 6 ft-lb) and loaded to failure. Additional panels of each type were subjected to a range of low level impacts from 1.4 to 8.1 Joules (1 to 6 ft-lb). These impact survey specimens were then ultrasonically C-scanned and sectioned for damage assessment of the facesheet and core. Graphical comparisons of delamination areas, dent depths, and core damage areas are included. Results indicate superior performance of the TPC and Nomex cores in both impact resistance and residual strength over the other honeycombs tested. Both exhibit residual compressive strengths of 80 to 90 % with only localized core crushing in the impact region. The glass reinforced thermosets exhibit a core cracking failure, while the aluminum cores propagate a permanent set buckle in the cell walls around the impact area.

KEYWORDS: Sandwich Construction ; Core,honeycomb ; Delamination;
Durability ; Compression After Impact

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials for structural applications can result in significant weight savings over similar metal designs. These weight savings result primarily from the reduced density of

composites, and the ability to tailor their laminate orientations to react applied loads. Further reduction in panel density can be achieved through the use of sandwich construction consisting of two load carrying facesheets bonded to low density core material. The core thickness determines the panel stiffness, while the facesheets provide the necessary in-plane strength. The ability to tailor the facesheets for optimum strength with no additional ply requirements for panel stiffness give composite sandwich structure the best strength/weight ratio for buckling applications.

A major concern with composite sandwich panel structures is their susceptibility to low level impact damage (tool drop, hail, runway debris). Low energy damage generally effects the outer facesheet only and maintains a continuous load path in the inner facesheet. Energy absorption modes for composite sandwich panels include matrix cracking, fiber fracture, inter-ply delaminations, fiber/matrix debond, and core failures. A great deal of research has been conducted to quantify laminate failures, but little has been done to evaluate the core failure modes effect on structural durability and performance. These core failure modes and energy absorption characteristics are dependent upon many parameters including core materials, density, cell size, and wall thickness.

A variety of honeycomb core materials were tested under Air Force Contract F33615-88-C-3202 (Reference 1). The objective was to determine the cores effect on both the damage characteristics and residual in-plane compression strength of composite sandwich panels. The facesheets were toughened Graphite/epoxy (IM8/8551-7A) in thicknesses of 0.51 mm (0.020", 4 plies) or 1.02 mm (0.04", 8 plies). Both facesheet types had fiber orientations of 50% 0° fibers and 50% ±45° fibers to maintain equivalent moduli for compression strength testing. The core thickness for all specimens and impact characterization was held constant at 1.27 mm (0.5").

2. DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION

The seven core types selected include two aluminum cores [32kg/m³ (2.0 pcf) and 61 kg/m³(3.8 pcf)], two aramid paper cores [29kg/m³ (1.8 pcf) and 48kg/m³(3.0 pcf)], two fiberglass reinforced thermoset cores [both 64kg/m³(4.0 pcf)], and one fiberglass reinforced thermoplastic core (64kg/m³). Each core type was bonded to Gr/Ep facesheets and cut into test specimens. A 127 mm by 610 mm (5" by 24") strip of each sandwich panel type was subjected to a range of

impacts from 0.7 J (0.5 ft-lb) to 8.1 J (6.0 ft-lb). Visual inspection and dent depth measurements determined the threshold of detectability, corresponding to a 1.3 mm (0.05") dent. The panels were ultrasonically inspected for delamination area measurements, and each strip was cut through the centerline of the impacted areas to visually inspect the extent of impact damage to the core. Figure 1 shows a comparison of three different core types with similar facesheets impacted at the same energy levels.

2.1 Impact Method The impact method used a 0.91 kg (2.0 lb) falling tube with a 12.7 mm (0.5") diameter spherical tip. The impactor was caught on the rebound to prevent multiple impacts. The specimens were fully supported on a flat steel plate to simulate the worst impact conditions (ie impact of a sandwich skin directly over supporting substructure).

2.2 Delamination Measurement and Trends A sample ultrasonic pulse echo CSCAN of an impact survey panel with HRP glass reinforced core with 8 ply facesheets is shown in Figure 2. The oval shaped delaminations due to impact are clearly visible, and overlap according to the orientations at the ply interface where they occur. As the impact energy increases, the delamination size increases to a maximum level, which in this case is 5.4 J (4.0 ft-lb). Damage is now clearly visible on the panel surface. Higher impact levels at 6.8 and 8.1 J (5.0 and 6.0 ft-lb) begin to penetrate the facesheet, and the interply delaminations cease to grow larger. These results are similar to those reported in Reference 2 and may be attributed to a change in the mode of energy absorption from interply delamination to core crushing and fiber breakage. The maximum delamination areas of the facesheet rarely exceeded 4 times the area of the impactor, and the most severe delaminations were observed between the innermost plies of the impacted facesheets.

The results for the thin 4 ply facesheet panels are shown in Figure 3. The threshold of damage detectability is 2.0 J (1.5 ft-lb), and facesheet penetration occurs at approximately 4.0 J (3.0 ft-lb). The data for each core type has two distinct areas, represented in the chart by diagonal and horizontal lines. The initial sloping portion shows the average rate of delamination growth with increasing impact energy. The knee between the lines occurs in the region of complete facesheet penetration. Beyond

this point, the delamination area around the impactor remained fairly constant, and is represented by the horizontal lines. The HRH-10 Nomex core displayed somewhat better durability trends than the NP or HRP cores due to a slightly lower rate of delamination growth, and less total delamination area at complete penetration.

2.3 Effects of Core Matrix on Delaminations Delamination data for the three fiberglass reinforced core types HRP, NP, and TPC, with 8 ply facesheets are shown in Figure 4. Delamination trends are illustrated by simple curves fit to each data set, and the vertical line represents visible . The HRP core has a phenolic resin matrix, the NP core uses a nylon modified phenolic base resin with final dips in polyester, and the TPC core uses a thermoplastic matrix. All three cores have the same density of 64 kg/m³ (4.0 pcf). Delamination areas for the HRP core were 25% to 65% greater than those of either NP or TPC. The phenolic resin matrix of the HRP makes the core stiff and brittle, tending to crack when impacted. The increased ductility of the polyester and thermoplastic matrix systems resulted in less severe facesheet delaminations.

2.4 Effects of Core Density on Delaminations Aluminum and Nomex delamination areas with 8 ply facesheets are shown in Figure 5. The aluminum honeycomb cores are represented by the black symbols, while HRH-10 Nomex honeycomb cores are white. The effects of core density on facesheet delamination area for similar impact energy levels can be observed directly from the figure. The lower density 'softer' cores displayed facesheet delamination areas from 40 to 50% smaller than those of the same core type in a heavier 'stiff' version. The largest delaminations resulted from use of the 61 kg/m³ (3.8 pcf) aluminum core, with slightly smaller areas for the 48 kg/m³ (3.0 pcf) Nomex core. It is interesting to note that this result disagrees with the conclusions presented in Reference 3, where softer cores had slightly larger delamination areas. Further analysis of the local facesheet and core failures were obtained by cutting the panels down the centerline of the impacts, and is described below.

2.5 Honeycomb Core Failure Modes Honeycomb core failure modes were evaluated by inspection of the sectioned impact survey strips. Because buckling is dependent upon wall thickness, aluminum cores tend to buckle along their thin cell walls when

impacted. The glass reinforced phenolic cores exhibit an entirely different mode of failure under the same impact conditions. Their cell walls are thicker, limited by the thinnest possible weave of fiberglass cloth, and the resin that binds them together is relatively brittle. When impacted, these cores tend to crack parallel to the facesheet, near the skin/core bondline, rather than buckle like a metallic core. The extent of this crack may be 2 or 3 times the diameter of the facesheet delamination area. Figure 6 shows a cross section of 6.8 and 8.1 J (5.0 and 6.0 ft-lb) impacts on the glass reinforced HRP 64 kg/m³ (4 pcf) core. The crack is clearly visible in both cases.

The core damage areas were measured at each impact level for the sectioned impact survey panels. Measurements were taken with a micrometer across the diameter of the damaged area. The diameters were approximated as the furthest visible extent of core cracking or cell wall buckling from the impact zone. Measuring damage in the glass reinforced and metallic cores was relatively easy due to the visible core failure modes described previously, but the Nomex cores displayed little or no damage up to levels of clearly visible facesheet damage. If local cell wall buckling occurred below this level, the aramid walls were able to spring back into shape without visible damage. The total core damage areas were assumed to be circular about the impacted region, and were calculated from the measured damage diameters.

Core damage trends for sandwich panels with 4 ply facesheets are shown in Figure 7. The three core types tested were HRP and NP glass reinforced 64 kg/m³ (4.0 pcf) honeycomb, and HRH-10 Nomex 48 kg/m³ (3.0 pcf) honeycomb. The two glass reinforced cores displayed similar damage trends due to the core crack propagation, while the Nomex displayed only localized crushing. In general, the core damage areas of the glass cores were 3 times greater than those of the Nomex.

Sandwich panels with 8 ply facesheets displayed greater magnitudes of core damage than originally anticipated. The impact locations were spaced every 50 mm (2"), and three core damage areas exceeded this limit, overlapping each other and eliminating the ability to calculate accurate core damage areas, as shown in Figure 8. The greatest propagation of core damage occurred with 32 kg/m³ (2.0 pcf) aluminum. The cell walls are very thin to maintain low density,

and therefore subject to buckling failures. The relatively 'soft' support provided by this core cushioned the blow to the facesheet (the delamination areas were very small as shown in Figure 5), and the majority of the impact energy was absorbed by buckling large areas of the core. The higher density aluminum core at 61 kg/m^3 (3.8 pcf) has thicker cell walls providing greater stiffness to the core. The core buckling damage is localized to the impact area, and did not exceed 1000 mm^2 (1.5 in^2). Energy absorption for this panel is attributed primarily to facesheet delaminations and fiber breakage.

The glass reinforced cores with 8 ply facesheets displayed a much larger extent of core damage than similar panels with 4 ply facesheets. Core damage areas were 3 to 4 times as great up to the area limit where damage overlap began to occur. The large magnitude of core damage is not certain, but may result from higher out-of-plane stiffness of the 8 ply facesheets resulting in a larger 'footprint' for the impact load. The Nomex and TPC honeycomb core damage areas were localized to the impact region. The resilience and ductility of these cores made visual damage inspection difficult. They displayed neither the permanent set buckling of the aluminum nor the cracking failures of the FG/Thermoset cores. Localized crushing of the cell walls in the impact region was observed, but did not exceed 330 mm^2 (0.50 in^2) at any impact level for these core types.

2.6 Dent Depth Measurements Dent depth survey results for sandwich panels fabricated from Nomex HRH-10 48 kg/m^3 (3.0 pcf) core with 4 ply and 8 ply Gr/Ep facesheets are shown in Figure 9. A linear relationship of facesheet thickness to dent depth was observed, and twice the impact energy was required to produce an equivalent dent in the 8 ply laminate as in the 4 ply laminate. A line has been drawn representing a minimum visible dent depth of 1.3 mm (0.05 in). This line corresponds to a 2.4 J (1.8 ft-lb) impact on the 4 ply facesheet and 5.2 J (3.8 ft-lb) impact on the 8 ply facesheet.

The effect of core type variation on dent depth is shown in Figure 10 for 8 ply facesheets at impact levels of 2.7 , 5.4 , and 8.1 J (2.0 , 4.0 , and 6.0 ft-lb). The 29 kg/m^3 (1.8 pcf) Nomex core maintained the shallowest dent depths, while the 5056 aluminum

showed the largest dent depths. This result is not unexpected, considering the failure mode of the core materials. The buckled walls of the aluminum core force the local area of the panel into a permanent set, while the resilient Nomex reinforced core allows the facesheet to spring back into shape.

3. RESIDUAL COMPRESSION STRENGTH

A test matrix was developed to evaluate the strength retention of post impact sandwich panels. Impact levels were chosen to represent non visible, barely visible, and clearly visible damage. The selected impact energies were 2.7, 5.4, and 8.1 J (2, 4, and 6 ft-lb) for the 8 ply facesheet specimens, and 1.4, 2.7, and 5.4 J (1, 2, and 4 ft-lb) for the 4 ply specimens. The test matrix includes three specimens at each impact level, in addition to three control (non-impact) specimens for each core type. All seven core types were tested with 8 ply facesheets, and three core types (HRP, NP and HRH-10) were tested with 4 ply facesheets. The specimens were 76 mm(3") by 127 mm(5") with 12.7 mm(0.5") thick honeycomb core, and were loaded in edgewise compression with the load axis parallel to the long dimension of the specimen. Previous studies (Reference 4) indicate the compression face wrinkling failure produced by edgewise compression testing is also representative of in-plane shear failure modes. Therefore, these tests relate to buckling critical sandwich panels loaded in compression or shear .

The results of this impact study for 8 ply facesheet specimens are presented graphically in Figure 11. The average compressive strength of each specimen type at failure is plotted versus the impact energy level. A clear trend of decreasing residual panel strength with increasing impact energy was characteristic of all core types.

3.1 Fiberglass Honeycomb Specimens The best non-impacted baseline panel strength was obtained with HRP glass reinforced 64 kg/m³(4.0 pcf) core specimens. Their ultimate panel failure stress of 386 MPa(56.0 ksi) is over 80 percent of the ultimate unnotched compression stress (478 MPa = 69.4 ksi) derived from material characterization tests of IM8/ 8551-7A laminates with 50/50/0 fiber orientations (Reference 1). The TPC and NP core specimens had baseline panel strengths of 372 and 317 MPa(54 and 46 ksi), respectively. The residual compression strength with easily

visible damage (8.1 J or 6 ft-lb) was highest for the TPC core at 80%, with NP and HRP at lower respective values of 72% and 63%.

3.2 Aluminum Honeycomb Specimens The 61 kg/m³ (3.8 pcf) 5056 aluminum core specimens displayed levels of post impact strength retention similar to the TPC core. Panel baseline strength was 352 MPa (51.1 ksi), 73% of the unnotched compression ultimate, and 95% of the TPC baseline strength. Compression strength after impact was 83%. The 32 kg/m³ (2.0 pcf) aluminum core is not shown, but had a baseline strength of 207 MPa (30 ksi) with 8.1 joule (6 ft-lb) strength retention of 62%. The low baseline strength is due to the poor facesheet support provided by the lower density core.

3.3 Aramid Honeycomb Specimens The baseline compression strength for the HRH-10 48 kg/m³ (3.0 pcf) specimens at 287 Mpa (41.7 ksi) were 20% to 25% lower than those of the fiberglass reinforced cores due to the lower flatwise compression properties of the Nomex. The residual strength for this core was excellent, with the highest post impact strength retention of any core (85%) at the 6 ft-lb impact level. The 29 kg/m³ (1.8 pcf) core is not shown, but had a baseline strength of 167 MPa (24.3 ksi) with 8.1 J (6 ft-lb) strength retention of 54%. Thus, an increase in core density from 29 kg/m³ to 48 kg/m³ (+67%) for the Nomex honeycomb core resulted in a baseline panel strength increase of 71%, and post impact strength increase of 172% .

3.4 Thin 4 Ply Facesheet Specimens The impact study results for 4 ply facesheet specimens are shown in Figure 12. Three non-metallic core specimen types were tested, including HRP 64 kg/m³ (4.0 pcf), NP 64 kg/m³ (4.0 pcf), and HRH-10 Nomex 48 kg/m³ (3.0 pcf) honeycomb. Impact levels for these thin facesheets were 1.4, 2.7 and 5.4 J (1.0, 2.0, and 4.0 ft-lb). The 8.1 J (6 ft-lb) specimens were not tested for post impact strength because full facesheet penetration had already occurred at the 5.4 J level for all core types. The threshold of damage detectability was 2.0 J (1.5 ft-lb) based upon impact survey inspections described in Section 1. Therefore, for the 4 ply facesheets, the non-visible damage threshold was represented by 1 ft-lb impacts, barely visible damage by 2 ft-lb, and clearly visible by 4 ft-lb impacts.

Evaluation of the test results indicate superior performance for the glass reinforced cores over the Nomex when thin facesheets are

used. The compressive properties of the core became more critical as facesheet thickness decreases because thin facesheets have less buckling stability in compression. The core must therefore provide a rigid buckling constraint in the transverse direction to prevent facesheet buckling and consequent panel failure. Flatwise compression test results of the various core materials (Reference 1) have indicated compression moduli for the glass reinforced core to be three times as great as that of Nomex. The stiffer facesheet support provided by the glass cores yielded higher failure stress levels for these specimens, even though they sustained larger areas of delamination and core damage (See Figs 3,7) than the Nomex panels.

4. SUMMARY OF RESULTS/CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions regarding the impact resistance and residual compression strength of the composite sandwich panels tested in this program are as follows:

1) The increased ductility of the polyester and thermoplastic matrix systems resulted in less severe facesheet delaminations.

2) The lower density 'softer' cores displayed facesheet delamination areas from 40 to 50% smaller than those of the same core type in a heavier 'stiff' version.

3) When impacted, FG/thermoset cores tend to crack parallel to the facesheet, near the skin/core bondline, rather than buckle like a metallic core. The extent of this crack may be 2 or 3 times the diameter of the facesheet delamination area.

4) The Nomex and TPC honeycomb core damage areas were localized to the impact region and did not exceed 330 mm² (0.50 in²) at any impact level.

5) The stiffer facesheet support provided by the FG cores yielded higher failure stress levels for these specimens, even though they sustained larger areas of delamination and core damage than the Nomex core panels.

6) The TPC FG/thermoplastic core displayed the best overall durability characteristics with high baseline panel strengths, and 80% strength retention with easily visible facesheet damage.

5. REFERENCES

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Impact Level :
8.1 J (6.0 ft-lb)

5056 Aluminum Core
61 kg/m³ (3.8 pcf)

HRH-10 Nomex Core
48 kg/m³ (3.0 pcf)

HRP Fiberglass Core
64 kg/m³ (4.0 pcf)

Figure 1. Impact Damage of Honeycomb Sandwich Panels with 8 Ply Facesheets

Figure 2. Pulse Echo C-Scan of HRP Honeycomb 8 Ply Panel

Figure 3 : Delamination Vs. Impact Energy, 4 ply Facesheets

* (1.00 ft-lb = 1.36 Joules)

Figure 4 : Delamination Vs. Impact Energy, 8 ply Facesheets, Fiberglass Cores

* (1.00 ft-lb = 1.36 Joules)

Figure 5 : Effect of Core Density on Delamination Areas with 8 ply Facesheets

* (1.00 ft-lb = 1.36 Joules)

Figure 6. Post-Impact Cracking of Fiberglass/Thermoset HRP Core

Figure 7 : Core Damage Area Vs. Impact Level, 4 Ply Facesheets

* (1.00 ft-lb = 1.36 Joules)

Figure 8 : Core Damage Vs. Impact Energy, 8 Ply Facesheets

Figure 9 : Effect of Facesheet Thickness on Dent Depth

Figure 10 : Dent Depth Vs. Impact Energy, 8 Ply Facesheets

* (1.00 ft-lb = 1.36 Joules)

Figure 11 : Compressive Strength Vs. Impact Energy, 8 Ply Facesheets

* (1000 psi = 6.894 MPa)

Figure 12 : Compressive Strength Vs. Impact Energy, 4 Ply Facesheets